

PRESERVATION OF ENVIRONMENT THROUGH ECO-FRIENDLY STEPS

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ABSTRACT

The word eco-friendly is actually derived from Ecosystem which is related to human beings and their habits. The term eco-friendly means those steps which are friendly to our ecosystem and environment, that do not hurt our earth's health and wealth. Earth is the wonderful creation of god. To save this beauty nature keeps balance among environmental components through ecosystem. If it is disturbed in any case, it affects the health of the earth. Environment is our natural heritage, and as a social creature it is the moral duty of every person to save this valuable property. So to save this environment, we should be eco-friendly.

Basically environment is made up of biotic and abiotic components present around us. They all maintain clean, balanced, perfect environment by keeping a proper balance and relation. Our environment is a rich source of natural resources.

Keywords:

Eco-friendly, Environment, earth's health and wealth.

INTRODUCTION

In ancient times, India is considered a country where the rivers of milk flow it means there was abundance of natural resources but as gradually the culture and the materialism develop the decomposition in the environment occurs rapidly. Eventually, people has to face the problem of pollution, global warming, over-population, natural resource depletion, waste disposal, loss of biodiversity, climate change, greenhouse effect, flood, drought, acid-rain, land-slide, hole in ozone layer, deforestation, worldliness, globalization, industrialization, urbanization, ocean acidification, public health issue etc. These all damage the balance in nature. So, these current environmental problems require urgent attention and a need of to be eco-friendly is realized.

These burning problems and issues shake whole of the world. People and government try to save this valuable treasure in any case. Finally the first step should be taken by a person individually to conserve the environment. Only some careful attention may cure this degenerated and unhealthy environment by making some personal efforts. Some small changes in our daily routine life can make us eco-friendly. The role of 3-R s (Reuse, Reduce, and Recycle) is very significant. In this concern some beneficial steps should be started from home.

TO SAVE WATER

Water supply takes a long procedure and energy to come to home. Every drop of water is precious. If we care, we should turn off the tap while the water is not in use at the time of washing clothes, utensils, shaving, brushing, bathing, etc. the value of 3-R s is applicable here- by turning the tap

off we can reduce unnecessary flowing of water. Reuse the remaining water, after washing clothes and utensils, in toilets and watering the plants and trees. Recycling of water should be done.

- Rain water should be collected.
- Water harvesting system should be made compulsory while the construction of building on the government level to save more water.
- Water should not be polluted by putting garbage, waste and chemicals into it.

Besides it, to stop water pollution, initial step should be taken by the government by issuing the orders to make eco-friendly statues of Gods and Goddesses on Hindu festivals.

TO SAVE ELECTRICITY

It is also started from the home.

- Make habit of switching off the lights and fans while leaving the room and office.
- Switch off the T.V., laptop, and computer when not in use.
- Overnight charging of mobiles should be avoided.
- We should use LED lights which are less energy consuming.
- The system of solar energy should be used. Today in many hospitals, hotels and houses, builders are providing solar geysers and solar lights to make the surroundings sound and pollution free and the concept behind it is to be eco-friendly, energy saving and cost efficient.
- We must avoid the maximum use of A.C. in homes and offices. The building should be airy so that more and more air and light must enter the room to enlighten it.

Recently, the Kochi International Airport of Kerala has been made the World's first solar energy operated Airport. 47 thousand solar panels were planted which will provide 50 to 60 thousand units of electricity. It will stop emission of 0.3 million metric ton of carbon dioxide which is equivalent to 3 million trees.

Moreover, windmills are also made to reduce the excessive use of energy and the excessive use of fuel should also be reduced.

AVOID CHEMICALS AND COSMETICS

Toxic chemicals are used in medicines, cosmetic, fertilizers, edible products, daily need items, pesticides, etc which are harmful not only for human beings but also for environment. With these following steps, these harmful effects can be avoided:-

- Organic and bio fertilizers, green manure, vermicompost be used in place of chemicals and pesticides.
- In cosmetics, natural and herbal products should be used.
- Natural perfumed oils, scents also provide sweet fragrance. The research are being made by many research institutions like IHBT (Palampur), IIIM (Jammu), etc,
- Natural essence and natural color should be used.

Finally it is clear from above data that eco-friendly steps basically have least negative impact on land, water and air. So it is moral, social and personal responsibility of every person to use more and more nontoxic, recyclable and bio degradable products to maintain less polluted and neat and clean environment. We should use more and more natural, handmade and eco-friendly products rather than toxic, artificial and fashionable products. So some plans, policies, bans should be imposed on people and industries to conserve the environment and to stop the disturbance and unbalance in nature. As a true friend of nature, a person must care for his surroundings and environment and be less harmful to his ecosystem.

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